

TEMPORARY PROSTHETICS FOR THE PERIOD OF OSSEOINTEGRATION OF IMPLANTS**Akhmedov Said Ilham***Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, Associate Professor***Rustamov Elshan Anvar***Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, Assistant***Huseynova Çeshmə Bahadur qızı***Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, Assistant**Azerbaijan Medical University, Department of Orthopedic Dentistry**Baku, Azerbaijan***Abstract**

One of the pressing problems in orthopedic dentistry is the timely replacement of defects in the dentition and the prevention of their deformations, optimal preservation of the volume of tissue of the prosthetic bed after tooth extraction surgery and the prevention of diseases of the temporomandibular joint. Finding ways to improve the effectiveness of treatment of patients in the period from tooth extraction to the manufacture of a permanent orthopedic structure, as well as methods that help reduce bone tissue atrophy, remains one of the most important tasks of orthopedic dentistry.

Key words: osseointegration of implants, immediate dentures, manufacturing methods.

The rapid development of implantation, nanotechnology and bone-substituting materials can significantly expand the indications for fixed prosthetics [2]. Long-term absence of teeth, as well as the early use of removable dentures, leads to loss of bone volume in the alveolar processes, which requires bone grafting and delayed prosthetics [5, 9], thereby increasing the treatment period to 1 year or more. The use of removable immediate prostheses at the stages of osseointegration has significant limitations, and sometimes is completely impossible [1.4.10]. Osteoplasty in most cases does not allow the production of immediate prostheses supported by installed implants. But the presence of defects of this kind negatively affects the psycho-emotional and physical health of a person in society [7, 8]. The decision on long-term treatment with the use of bone grafting and replacement of dentition defects with implantation will also depend on the proposed temporary prosthetics [3, 6]. The cost of temporary dentures also plays an important role. The purpose of the study is to create a temporary structure that replaces the defect and does not exert excessive pressure on the area with insufficient bone tissue in the area of the planned implantation. This design should contribute to the rapid rehabilitation of patients and their social adaptation at the stages of preparation for dental implantation surgery and the further use of the prosthetic design for the period of osseointegration of implants with a renewed bone base, as well as restore the height of the lower part of the face and occlusal contacts of the dentition before permanent prosthetics.

Material and methods.

We have proposed a method for manufacturing a direct prosthesis for the period of osseointegration of implants with bone grafting of the alveolar processes in the form of a mouthguard, which is carried out as follows. Anatomical impressions are obtained from both jaws before the planned implantation with bone grafting. One set of models of the upper and lower jaws is made. Central occlusion or centric relation is determined using bite blocks and the model is fixed into the articulator. Using a computed tomogram of the jaws

(obtained earlier), toothless areas of the alveolar process are determined for installation of implants with insufficient bone volume, the corresponding areas are restored on the model and the undercuts are isolated. In the area of missing teeth, artificial teeth are modeled using "Renfert GEO Classic Natural" wax on the area of the alveolar process restored with modeling wax. In this case, an individual shape of the teeth is created, focusing on adjacent and antagonist teeth. The boundaries of the future immediate prosthesis are marked on the model, which will depend on the individual anatomical characteristics of the patient, the degree of atrophy of the alveolar processes, the type of mucous membrane and topography of the frenulum, as well as on the planned volume of bone grafting. The borders of the mouth guard will have a supragingival part in the area of all teeth: not only the removed ones, but also the remaining ones. Also (and this is of utmost importance for the redistribution of chewing pressure) the boundaries will overlap the unaffected parts of the alveolar process by implantation and bone grafting, including the hard palate. The mouthguard is made by vacuum thermoforming using Easy-vak Gasket plates and cut along previously determined boundaries, the edges are carefully polished. On the upper jaw, the palatal part of the mouth guard is not cut off. After washing and drying in the area of missing teeth, the tray is filled with cold-curing plastic "GC Tempron" up to the necks of the previously modeled teeth, while the shape of the teeth in the tray exactly matches the previously modeled wax teeth. The mouth guard with the teeth is fitted and applied immediately after surgery in the oral cavity, making sure that there is no contact of the mouth guard with the alveolar process, in the area of which plastic surgery was performed and implants were installed. 7-10 days after the operation, consultation with the surgeon and removal of the sutures directly in the oral cavity, the area of bone grafting in the tray is filled with soft plastic Mollosil A-silicone (Detax, Germany), which has antibacterial properties. Thanks to this, the chewing pressure from the mouth guard on the area of implantation with plastic surgery is more gentle, and

the mouth guard itself does not touch this area with its rigid base and edges. The tray is first coated on the inside in the area of the alveolar ridge and palate with the adhesive included in the A-silicone kit, which ensures the durability of the elastic lining. Also, the soft lining is an excellent insulator of the mucous membrane from possible diffusion of residual monomer of self-hardening cold-curing plastic.

Results. We obtained positive clinical results with the use of temporary aligners in 14 patients (10 women, 4 men aged 42-55 years) with dentition defects of Kennedy classes I, II, III and IV of the upper and lower jaws with insufficient bone volume in the area installation of planned implants.

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